

2 Poems by Nurbek Norchayev

translated by Nodira Ibrahimova

We are a single leaf

standing on the Tree of Life.
Bound to the body by the heart's emotions,
so long as breath remains
we are praying.
From the fairy tales of youth's spring,
at times we long to whisper
into the ear of a blossom.
Yet our hidden secrets
we tell to You alone
You who can listen to everyone
at the same moment.
You are Almighty, O God!
You bestowed valleys upon the deer,
wide tablecloths spread for them.
To what fate did You inscribe
eternal destiny, my Lord,
Like inscriptions carved in rock and stone?!

I am a spark of fortune, a flame of bliss,
A rare and singular find of destiny.
is it careless? The eyes don't notice.

Bearing the weighty stones of time,
Human lives, testing the strength to endure.
The swift steed of time still never halts.

One wall divides the darkness and light,
One wall divides the two eternal worlds.
This world even does not resemble paradise.

Poems are translated by Nodira Ibrahimova is a laureate of the international award named after Muhammad Reza Ogahi

Bio:

Nurbek Norchayev was born in 1993 in Koson, Qashqadaryo, Uzbekistan. He is a contemporary Uzbek poet known for his heartfelt and emotional poetry. His works often explore themes of love, human values, and the beauty of life and nature.

Through his words, Nurbek captures deep emotions and touches the hearts of his readers, making his poetry a vivid reflection of modern Uzbek literature.